

Marketing of Advanced Materials Intellectual Property

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SUMMARY :

INTRODUCTION

The annual licensing survey for FY 1996 released by the Association of University Technology Managers (AUTM) confirmed that the transfer of research conducted at academic research institutions to companies plays a vital role in the U.S. economy. AUTM estimates that sales of products developed from inventions made in the course of academic research and licensed to industry amounted to \$20.6 billion in 1996. The volume of technology transfer activity demonstrates that industry not only needs the creativity and innovation of academic research, but also values the active participation in the process of building partnerships.

The Bayh-Dole Act of 1980 (U.S. Public Law 96-517) requires US university technology transfer offices to market the inventions universities create using federal research funds. The experience at U.S. universities is that marketing ranges from mailing a list of disclosures to participating in trade shows to web pages to reacting to leads provided by faculty. The experience at Virginia Tech Intellectual Properties, Inc. (VTIP) is that valuation, identification of prospective licensees, negotiating terms, and contract language is different for advanced materials than for inventions based on life science. This paper will explore these differences and give examples of successful programs.

1.0 University Intellectual Property and Economic Development

Economic development through exploitation of intellectual property is now widely touted as one of the major benefits of federally sponsored research. This effect was given a major boost by the passage of the Bayh-Dole Act (Public Law 96-517), implemented in 1980. The primary intent of

this law was to foster the growth of technology-based small businesses by allowing them to own the patents that arose out of federally sponsored research.

Universities and other nonprofit recipients of federal funding were included in the definition of "small entities" benefiting from the Bayh-Dole Act, largely as an afterthought. Under the Bayh-Dole Act, the universities themselves would not develop the patented technologies, but would license the patents to industry. A provision of the law allowed the universities to retain royalties from such licensing and specified that a fraction of the royalties would be shared as personal income to the inventors. By law, the university's share of the royalties must be plowed back into its research and educational activities.

A key aspect of university licensing of their inventions under Bayh-Dole was the granting of exclusivity. How could the federal government justify allowing a single company to be given the advantage of intellectual property developed under taxpayer funding? The universities pointed out that exclusive licenses were imperative for the development of early-stage technology. The commercial licensee must devote substantial time and money to attempt to develop the technology, with no guarantee that it will be successful. Exclusive licenses are an inducement and reward for a company willing to step forward and take such a risk--knowing that if it succeeds in the development, the exclusive license will protect it from more risk-averse competitors.

Now almost all research universities in the United States have technology licensing operations. The number of U.S. patents granted to American universities in a year rose from about 300 in 1980 to almost 2000 in 1995. The top American research universities earned a total of more than \$336-million from licenses on their inventions in 1996 and were awarded 1,776 new patents, according to a survey by the Association of University Technology Managers. The royalty figure is about 23 per cent higher than the comparable number for 1995.

Of the 2,209 licenses and options executed by universities in 1996, about 64 per cent went to small businesses, defined as those with fewer than 500 employees. Just over half of the licenses and options universities signed in 1996 gave a company the exclusive rights to an invention. The survey also showed that in 1996, universities formed 184 start-up companies based on technology developed at the institution and licensed to the new business.

More than 250 new companies were formed directly through university licenses in 1996--and a total of more than 1900 companies since the inception of the Bayh-Dole Act in 1980. Hundreds of products are already on the market that were developed under licenses--ranging from new vaccines to computer security systems, electronic music chips, chemotherapeutic agents, and low-pollution industrial burners.

The direct economic impact of technology licensing on the universities themselves has been relatively small (a surprise to many who believed that royalties could compensate for declining federal support of research). Although a very few, and highly visible, "blockbuster" inventions such as the Cohen-Boyer gene-splicing patent from Stanford University and the University of California, the fax patent owned by Iowa State, and the cis-platin patents of Michigan State University have made tens of millions for universities, most university licensing offices barely break even. In contrast, the impact of university technology transfer on the local and national economies has been substantial, and leads to the conclusion that the Bayh-Dole Act is one of the

most successful pieces of economic development and job-creation legislation in recent history. It has been estimated that more than 200,000 jobs have been created in the United States in product development and manufacturing of products from university licenses, with the number increasing fairly rapidly as the licenses mature.

These results of university licensing have been noted with great interest by local communities, state legislatures, the U.S. Congress, and many policy-makers abroad. State governments are setting aside moneys specifically to fund technology transfer offices and new-company incubators in their universities. The phrase "Bayh-Dole" is heard frequently in Japan and Germany as their educational ministries seek to emulate the U.S. university technology transfer system.

2.0 University Intellectual Property Market

Most US businesses and Universities are confused by the University Intellectual Property market. The structure of the market, the cultures and the reasons to come together are outside of their experience. The university Intellectual Property market is characterized best by the business process or flow of operations. In the university Intellectual Property flow, as opposed to the traditional business operations, none of the variables are under control. The university Intellectual Property office does not know when their raw material – disclosed inventions – will arrive at their doorstep. Nor, can they anticipate the quality of the disclosure. It could be the cure for cancer or the solution to a design problem for one composite material in one application. Once the disclosure is received, then the cost of the patenting process – the production process – cannot be forecasted. In fact, the office cannot even forecast the time to produce a patent. Outside of a copyright, which is immediate, a patent is the only product a university Intellectual Property office has.

Now that there is a patent, the office has no firm idea of who might be interested in applying this unique solution to a set of problems. The Intellectual Property offices have no confirmation that there are customers. If a licensee or customer is found, then the price or license fees and royalties are negotiated. That is once there is a customer then the price is negotiated. So, businesses work with a unit of the university that cannot anticipate the quality of its products, the cost of goods licensed, nor the does not know its cost. In a number of cases the university administration cannot understand why they have such an office.

The major source of confusion about Intellectual Property activities actually results from cultural perspectives. Each participant in the Intellectual Property market must deal with the reality of different cultures but similar pressures: changing funding, aging demographics, hierarchy moving to team based organizations, and global competitors. Universities and industry do view the world differently. Each has a different reward system; set research priorities according to different criteria; and even have a different measure of time as shown in the following matrix.

	University View	Industry View
Rewards	Grad. Students, Facilities, Salary, Peer Recognition	Profit, Bonuses, Standard of Living
Research Priorities	Peers, Curiosity	Market, Executives
Values	Freedom, Collaboration, Openness	Independence, Competition, Risk Reduction
Time	Semesters, Ph.D. Cycle	Weeks, Annual

The barriers to collaboration or licensing from a university that companies mention most often are:

- Lack of understanding by the faculty of the value of protecting technology.
- Most faculty know-how is difficult to access. Written records can be faulty or missing.
- Technology is overvalued by faculty, especially for early stage discoveries.
- Lack of a realistic appraisal of time, facilities, and capital required for commercialization.

As awareness of the need for industrial support for basic research grows on campus, most businesses and universities are becoming aware of the difficulties in establishing and managing these relationships. For the industrial executive and scientist, they need to compromise their traditional “work for hire” perspective to include the benefits of gaining access to world class, high risk research collaboration with qualitative benefits (corporate citizenship and access to new hires). For the university administrator and faculty, they need to move from a strict pursuit of curiosity driven research and intellectual freedom to the benefits of a time dependent research collaboration that provide a viable dissemination model for any discoveries.

Faculty and graduate students are rewarded by their peers if they publish and disseminate broadly their discoveries. The goal of the university Intellectual Property office is to create a “pause before publication”... to provide a researcher with the awareness of an alternative method for dissemination. University Intellectual Property offices create this “pause” through education and endorsement. Intellectual property practices and law is not a part of most faculty’s educational background. University Intellectual Property develops workshops; disseminates information on the Internet; and answers questions every chance they can.

3.0 Valuation

3.1 Valuation for University Decisions

Once a disclosure reaches the university Intellectual Property office, there are a number of paths that it can take, if it is to be commercialized. As a consequence, the first step of most University Intellectual Property offices is to evaluate the disclosure for technical merit – is the proposed solution to a problem robust and feasible. The next concern is commercial merit – does the invention solve an important problem in the market place. Last but not least, is the question – can this invention be protected by patent or copyright. The other traditional industrial protection – trade secret – is not an option because of the requirement for publication in the university culture.

The university Intellectual Property office must determine if there is sufficient value at this stage of development to invest limited patenting and marketing dollars. To help answer this initial

question, Virginia Tech Intellectual Properties, Inc. (VTIP) a number of hard copies are distributed to the Intellectual Property Committee (IPC) of Virginia Tech, a committee of faculty to interview the inventor. It is easier for peers to interview peers and to obtain more complete information, even for commercial value. The IPC assigns a faculty to interview the inventor and to answer the questions found below.

1. Stage of Development: This may range from conceptual (an idea with maybe some sketches) to essentially market ready (a fully developed, beta tested software package including complete user manuals, etc.). Both extremes are relatively rare, and identification/definition of “next steps” is extremely helpful.

Fatal flaws: None, but very early stage disclosures (idea stage) usually have low priority.

2. Development costs/time: This refers primarily to commitments and investments which a potential licensee would have to make to take the technology from its present stage to final sale/use. Large costs/long lead times spell high risk and therefore require high potential rewards to arouse commercial interest. Also in this category may be such factors as the technology being dependent on a related development (technical, regulatory, political, etc.) and/or solving a problem which is not currently high priority but which may become so in the future.

Fatal flaws: None, but high risk situations require early exploration of specific licensee interest prior to significant further resource commitment.

3. Technical merit: This may range from a marginal improvement to an existing product/process on one end to a basic breakthrough which revolutionizes a technical field or industry on the other extreme. Evaluation of this factor should weigh towards understanding of the technology rather than determination of its importance, since at times a marginal improvement which offers an elegant (and inexpensive) solution to a nagging problem can be both easy to commercialize and relatively profitable.

Fatal flaws: None, but technologies at either extreme require more than usual depth of exploration of other evaluation criteria.

4. Market Breadth: This factor should be examined from two aspects, namely field of use and geographic. Narrow markets often have the advantage of relatively simple marketing effort but are usually not large. The evaluation also should consider the possibility that there may be multiple uses for the technology, above and beyond those suggested by the problem(s) the inventors set out to solve; experience indicates that the alternates often exceed the base in market potential. In evaluating this factor, any information regarding potential licensees (industries, companies, individual contacts, etc.) are extremely valuable.

Fatal flaws: None, but if combined with small market size will easily result in low priority.

5. Market size: If at all possible, this factor should be defined in terms of dollars. A precise definition is usually not readily feasible or necessary, order of magnitude, “back of the envelope” estimates (with bases/assumptions) are normally quite adequate at this stage.

Fatal flaws: Revenues (units sold x unit sales price) of less than \$100,000 for technologies requiring patent protection.

6. Inventor(s)’s attitude: Throughout the commercialization process, which can take from a few months to several years, the inventor(s) have to be willing and able to “invest” time, effort, and skills in the activity, often with minimal (if any) short-term tangible rewards or benefits. Without such an “investment” a positive outcome is highly unlikely regardless of the technical-economic merits of the technology.

Determination of the degree of interest, attitude, and motivation of the inventor(s) towards the commercialization of a given technology is clearly subjective and rarely simple or clear-cut; it is, however, an area in which the contribution of the IPC evaluator may be both irreplaceable and extremely valuable.

Fatal flaws: An a-priori negative attitude towards the process, without the willingness to reconsider. An activity load such that no significant time can be made available in the foreseeable future; misguided motivation (e.g. “all I want from this is a patent in my publications list”).

In addition to the faculty committee, some universities also use graduate candidates to develop a market analysis. In order for this approach to be successful, the Intellectual Property office needs to provide:

- 1) supervision, preferably by an individual that has some market development experience. The graduate candidate will have someone they can go to for advise and direction.
- 2) an example of the expended content of the report. The student should include both a literature search and at least 3-5 market contacts. The student needs to acquire the experience of contacting businesses as part of their educational experience. The Intellectual Property office needs to know that the concept of the invention can be explained in simple terms for a potential licensee to understand and make a business decision.
- 3) compensation and a reasonable timeline for completion, but it must be in a commercial setting. Normally 3-4 weeks and the student should be paid \$300-500 per report.

3.2 Valuation for Licensing Negotiations

Following is a discussion of all valuation methods considered to determine the range of acceptable economic values as a starting point for negotiations. Ultimately, value is established between two parties across the table.

3.2.1. Cost Approach

The Cost Approach values Intellectual Property assets based on the cost to create and develop or to replace the assets under consideration. This valuation method is based on the premise that no party involved in an arm's-length transaction would be willing to pay more to use the property than the cost to replace the property. The estimated cost to develop the technology may be based upon historical development costs or the projected cost to develop an asset of similar value as of the date of valuation.

The Cost Approach allows for consideration of other cost elements involved in bringing the "replacement" asset to the same level of economic performance as the original asset had at the time of valuation. For instance, full replacement of a proprietary product may involve lost sales and profits during the period of development, as well as incremental marketing and promotional expenses to secure a comparable market position for the replacement product. The typical result of using the Cost Approach is a lump-sum value of the subject technology as opposed to a running royalty rate.

The main limitation of this approach is its lack of consideration for all elements of future income and/or profit streams, market conditions, useful life, and the risk associated with receiving future economic benefits. Another limitation of this approach is the inherent assumption that the asset is "replaceable" with one of equivalent value, an assumption that often does not apply to intellectual property, which is unique by definition.

Nonetheless, the Cost Approach may be a very appropriate method for valuing assets with certain characteristics. For example, this approach may be appropriate for valuing embryonic, basic technology for which market applications cannot yet be defined. Also, if the technology is narrow in scope and thus easy to replicate or "design around," the cost approach may be appropriate.

3.2.2 Market Approach

The Market Approach values assets based on comparable transactions between unrelated parties. Factors to consider include the nature of the assets transferred, the industry and products involved, agreement terms, and other factors, which may affect the agreed-upon compensation. There are two articles, *Licensing Practices, Business Strategy and Factors Affecting Royalty Rates: Results of a Survey* [1] and *A Survey of Licensed Royalties*, [2] which are surveys of licensing executives. The articles can provide a basis for the initial valuation.

3.2.3 Income Approach

For property dedicated to a business enterprise, including intellectual property, future benefits are preferably measured in terms of income generated by the Intellectual Property.[3]The Income Approach does just this, as it values assets based on the present value of the future income streams expected from the asset under consideration. The expected future cash flow stream from the asset, usually a series of periodic amounts, may be quantified using a variety of approaches depending on the specific circumstances of each case.

The duration and timing of the cash flow stream is determined by forecasting the useful life of the property, which can be determined in any one of several ways:

- ✓ the physical or service life of the asset
- ✓ the statutory or legal life of the asset
- ✓ the economic life of the asset - the period of time during which the property is producing an adequate return
- ✓ the functional or technological life - the period after which the technology becomes commercialized but before which the asset becomes technologically obsolete.

The business risk associated with the realization of the stream of expected cash flows may be captured through the use of an appropriate discount rate. The discount rate should reflect a rate of return on investment that is commensurate with the risk associated with the commercial exploitation of the assets under consideration. This discount rate is used to discount future

expected cash flows back to the present in the net present value calculation. In the context of valuing intellectual property, the Relief From Royalty Approach is frequently used.

3.2.3.1 Relief From Royalty Approach

The Relief From Royalty Approach is based on the following premise: a property's value can be measured by what the owner of the property would pay in royalties if it did not own the property and had to license it from a third party (i.e., the licensing costs avoided by virtue of owning the property). Conversely, this approach may also quantify the amount of income that the owner would generate by licensing the intellectual property to others.

This method requires that the Intellectual Property have been developed to the point where it can be expected that products encompassing the Technologies could be produced within a reasonable period of time. Second, there was sufficient data to develop reasonable estimates of the royalty base (i.e., projected revenues). Third, there was adequate data to support the determination of a reasonable royalty rate. Finally, the Relief From Royalty Approach accounts for market conditions, the economic life of the Technologies and the risk associated with receiving future economic benefits.

3.2.3.2 Methods for Determination of an Appropriate Royalty Rate

Market Approach - Market Approach entails searching for negotiated royalty rates from comparable licensing transactions.

Profit Apportionment Approach - A method used in court cases and in IRS regulations to determine a reasonable royalty rate under an arm's-length transaction scenario is to evaluate the share of the licensee's anticipated profit a licensor may seek in return for providing the licensee with access to the intellectual property. The need to split or share the anticipated profit "pool" between licensors and licensees of intellectual property has been recognized and endorsed by licensing practitioners, Tax Court case law, [4,5,6] and Internal Revenue Service regulations.[7] In the case of licensing intellectual property assets, there are several "rules of thumb" that are commonly employed when determining a reasonable profit split. A common rule of thumb is referred to as the "25% rule." Marcus B. Finnegan and Herbert H. Mintz provide a good overview of this rule in an article from The Business of Licensing [8]

"While the percentage may be variable depending upon the facts, there is fairly common acceptance of a figure of 25 percent of the profits earned by the licensee as a reasonable royalty to the licensor."

Excess Earnings Approaches - The Excess Earnings Approach values a property by the incremental earnings which may be achieved by the subject assets with intellectual property protection (e.g., a patent) relative to the profitability of similar "benchmarks." Examples of "benchmarks," as used here, may include profit margins on products without intellectual property protection or more general measures of normal industry profit levels. The "excess earnings" may result from the proprietary product commanding a price premium, delivering certain manufacturing cost savings, or achieving larger sales quantities.

Cost Savings Approach - Occasionally, the only income-enhancing contribution of an intellectual property is in the form of manufacturing (or other) cost savings that accrue to the owner (or licensee) of the property. In such cases, the quantum of the cost savings may constitute an appropriate basis for determination of a reasonable royalty rate. While there is certainly the potential for the Technologies to generate cost savings versus the "next-best alternative", the main advantage of the Technologies relates to their versatility in the design area, their acoustical properties and their use as a substitute product for many structural components. Because we did not have access to a specific licensee's cost structure, no cost savings data is

available. Therefore, we did not select the cost savings method to determine an appropriate royalty rate.

4.0 Marketing of Intellectual Property

Most universities have found that faculty have the best commercial contacts to find potential licensees. Our largest source of referrals is from faculty who have had a positive experience. Any public recognition that we can foster helps promote the concept of peer supported benefits from disclosing intellectual property to VTIP. Most often the question, "Is this a solution for a problem that the market believes it has?" University research agendas are not set by market concerns but rather by either curiosity of the investigators or understanding which problems are of interest to their peers, or by priorities of their governmental funding sources. As a result the solutions to the problems that the faculty offer as inventions are disconnected from the market place where the invention will be offered for commercialization. Some of the inventions could be simple incremental improvements to existing products or processes, most could be the basis for new product platforms, but some are the basis for new businesses, new industries.

Once a disclosure has been rated, then a marketing plan is established with the inventor. A list of target contacts and a draft non-proprietary description is developed. These contacts are made by phone or by mail with follow up. The objective is to identify a potential licensee that has the willingness and capability to commercialize the technology. If the discussion with the prospective licensee allows, a proposed commercialization plan is developed.

After a targeted contact has converted to a prospective licensee, then negotiations are undertaken to establish the contractual relationship. VTIP has a reasonable record, with 25-30 licenses per year from 80 plus disclosures per year. Of course the time from disclosure to license depends on the value of the technology - how important is the problem solved; the flexibility of the licensee - how big is the company; and the development state of the technology - how much investment is required to commercialize.

VTIP has had success in licensing to start-ups. We rank sixth in the nation in the percent of licenses to start-ups (35%) and ninth in ratio of new start-ups to \$10 million Federal Research Support (0.82 - MIT was 0.81 or tenth). VTIP has developed experience with a number of different models to assist in faculty spin-offs and entrepreneurial start-ups.

Equity in Lieu of License Fee and/or Patent Expense. All start-ups have one thing in common. They don't have enough cash. VTIP has directly taken equity in lieu of license fees and/or patent expenses in three firms and indirectly through CIT in three more firms. One has gone public and another is on track with a second round of financing. The average valuation for the stock was \$30,000, which represented less than 2% of the outstanding shares. Normally, VTIP does not request a board seat, and the ownership is usually under a non-dilution agreement up to an agreed level of capitalization.

Incubation of For-profit Subsidiary. VTLS is an example of using the strength of VTIP and the Virginia Tech Foundation to commercialize a technology. VTIP brought access to the technology and provided a financial umbrella. The inventor brought an existing customer base and a will to win. The exit scenario was a management buyout with an IRR of 25% to VTIP.

Investment in Seed Venture Capital. The probability of institutional investment is inversely proportional to the distance that the fund managing partner must travel. VTIP along with the

Foundation, has invested in Zero Stage, Triad/University Partners, InterSouth, and SpaceVest. These investments provide access to Virginia Tech start-ups if they have a solid business plan.

5.0 Commercialization of Composite Developments

The materials industry development structure, which is the basis of the composites industry, has some characteristics which are a combination of history and the capital requirement for production. When new materials are synthesized either at a University research center or in a corporate lab, they must be mixed with additives to make them useful for the targeted applications. The composites industry is structured into:

1. Basic Materials Suppliers - Large Chemical companies that synthesize and or polymerize materials; for the,
2. Compounders or Formulators - Combination of small and large companies that blend materials to meet specific market needs; from the,
3. End users - Combination of small and large companies that design, fabricate and or add value to manufactured parts with advanced materials.

Like most Physical Sciences, these various segments are now starting to express interest in how to license in technology that the Biotechnology has enjoyed since it started

Below are two charts that show a distribution of biotechnology deals over a 4-year period.

The major differences between the biotech and physical science deals are not the royalties, both are about the same. It is the license fees and milestone payments. Life science has a history of large upfront development costs and consider these fees as part of the cost. The return is much larger on successful life science deals than on physical science deals.

3.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

Commercialization partnerships between Universities and Industry have been enabled by the passage of the Bayh-Dole Act in 1980. The commercialization process begins with the valuation of the Intellectual Property to determine if an investment should be made in patenting. Then marketing identifies a prospective licensee to have discussions on the value as defined by the potential application of the technology. There are a number of methods to define that initial valuation for negotiations; ultimately, the value will be decided by the two parties negotiating.

Each party to the negotiations need to understand the differences in the cultures. It is those differences that determines the success factors for each side. Also, each side needs to understand that experience in other deals, whether business to business or university licensing to biotechnology, does not help in these negotiations.

REFERENCES

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² “A Survey of Licensed Royalties”, Stephan A. Degnan and Corwin Horton, les Nouvelles, June 1997, pp. 91-96.

³ Valuation of Intellectual Property and Intangible Assets, *Second Edition*, Gordon V. Smith and Russell L. Parr, John Wiley & Sons, New York, NY, 1994, p. 152.

⁴ Ciba-Geigy v. Comm’r, 85 T.C. 172, 229 (1985).

⁵ Bausch & Lomb v. Comm’r, 92 T.C. 525, 608, aff’d 91-1 USTC 50,244.

⁶ Hospital Corporation of America v. Comm’r, 81 T.C. 520, 601 (1983).

⁷ Section 482 of the Internal Revenue Code (§482).

⁸ “Determination of a Reasonable Royalty in Negotiating a License Agreement; Practical Pricing for Successful Technology Transfer”, Marcus B. Finnegan and Herbert H. Mintz, The Business of Licensing, Clark Boardman Company, Ltd., 1978, p. 3D-17.